

Kinetics and mechanism of the reactions of chromium(III) and L-ornithine in aqueous solution

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The anation reaction of L-ornithine (H_3L^{2+}) with chromium(III) has been studied over the range $3.0 \leq \text{pH} \leq 3.5$, $40^\circ \leq t \leq 55^\circ$ and $0.025 \leq [\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}] \leq 0.2$, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KNO_3). This reaction follows a mechanism which takes place via an outer sphere association between Cr^{3+} and (H_3L^{2+}) followed by transformation of the outer into an inner-sphere complex (chelate is formed) by slow interchange. The anation rate constant at 25° and $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KNO_3) is found to be $0.64 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger for k_{an} path are found to be $55.75 \pm 6.0 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-138.23 \pm 17.0 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. The reaction of Cr^{3+} with L-ornithine follows an associative interchange mechanism.

Substitution reactions of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ with various amino acids and other acids have been reported¹⁻⁵. Substitution reaction of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ takes place at the metal center via a transition state showing a greater degree of bond making with the incoming ligand than of bond breaking with the leaving ligand⁶. The present work describes the reaction of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ with L-ornithine in acid medium.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry and reaction products : Addition of acidic aquachromium(III) solution to a solution of L-ornithine resulted in an increase in absorbance in the visible range. The absorption spectra of the mixture (Cr^{3+} + L-ornithine) indicates the formation of a complex (Fig. 1). The shifting of λ_{max} from 560 nm to 540 nm is a clear indication of complex formation between Cr^{3+} and L-ornithine. The Job's curve also indicates the formation of 1 : 1 metal ligand complex by the reaction between Cr^{3+} and L-ornithine.

Effect of reaction rate on $[\text{H}^+]$: The reaction was studied at varying $[\text{H}^+]$, while keeping $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Cr}^{3+}]_{\text{T}} = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at different temperatures. It was observed that with the decrease in $[\text{H}^+]$, the k_{obs} values increased. Table 1 contains the pertinent data at 50° . To explain the $[\text{H}^+]$ dependence on the reaction rate, it is necessary to consider the dissociation of L-ornithine in the following manner.

With the decrease in $[\text{H}^+]$, the concentration of H_2L^+ , HL and L^- will increase in solution. Under the experimental conditions when pH has been varied from 3.0–3.5, the most active species involved in anation is most likely H_2L^+ . The

K_1 , K_2 and K_3 values⁷ of L-ornithine at 20° are 7.76×10^{-3} , 1.174×10^{-9} and 2.57×10^{-11} respectively. The hydrolysis constant⁸, K_h at 25° for $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ is 1.92×10^{-4} . Hence the amount of $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}^{2+}]$ will be quite small at $\text{pH} = 3.5$. The same explanation has been offered by other workers⁹.

Effect of reaction rate on L-ornithine concentration : The effect of $[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_{\text{T}}$ on the reaction rate was studied at fixed $[\text{H}^+]$ under varying temperature. The concentration of $[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_{\text{T}}$ was varied from 0.025 to 0.2 mol dm^{-3} at constant Cr^{3+} concentration. The results are presented in Table 1. It is observed that as $[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_{\text{T}}$ increases k_{obs} increases in a non linear fashion, indicating outer-sphere complex formation between Cr^{3+} and L-ornithine. The order of the

Fig. 1. Spectral difference among $[\text{Cr}(\text{OH}_2)_6]^{3+}$, $[\text{L-ornithine}]_T$ and the product complex : (1) $[\text{Cr}(\text{OH}_2)_6]^{3+} = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 3.5$, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at 50° , (2) $[\text{Cr}(\text{OH}_2)_6]^{3+} = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{L-ornithine}]_T = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 3.5$, $\text{temp.} = 50^\circ$ at zero min, (3) at 15 min, (4) at 30 min, (5) at 45 min, (6) at 90 min.

Fig. 2. $10^5 k_{\text{obs}}/\text{s}^{-1}$ vs $[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_T/\text{mol dm}^{-3}$. Conditions : $[\text{Cr}^{3+}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KNO_3), at 50° : (1) at $\text{pH} = 3.0$, (2) at $\text{pH} = 3.5$.

Table 1. Kinetic data for the anation reaction of Cr^{3+} with L-ornithine $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO_3), $\text{Temp.} = 50^\circ$

$[\text{Cr}^{3+}]_T$ mol dm^{-3}	$[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_T$ mol dm^{-3}	MeOH (%v/v)	pH	$10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ s^{-1}	$10^4 k_{\text{an}}$ s^{-1}	K_{OS}
0.005	0.025	0	3.0	8.93		
0.005	0.05	0	3.0	13.79		
0.005	0.10	0	3.0	17.72		
0.005	0.15	0	3.0	21.84		
0.005	0.20	0	3.0	25.62	3.42 ± 0.34	18.91 ± 2.7
0.005	0.025	0	3.5	13.26		
0.005	0.05	0	3.5	19.57		
0.005	0.10	0	3.5	24.77		
0.005	0.15	0	3.5	28.81		
0.005	0.20	0	3.5	31.95		
0.005	0.05	5	3.5	35.45		
0.005	0.05	10	3.5	37.50		
0.005	0.05	20	3.5	43.08		

reaction with respect to $[\text{L-ornithine}]$ is one up to $[\text{L-ornithine}] = 0.03 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at 50° , after that the order is less than one. This Michaelis-Menton type of plot (Fig. 2) also indicates the complex formation process between Cr^{3+} and L-ornithine.

Effect of reaction rate on $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$: In the first set of kinetic experiments, the $[\text{Cr}^{3+}]_T$ was varied at constant concentration of L-ornithine, ($[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_T = 0.05 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). The ionic strength, pH and temperature were kept constant. The pseudo-first-order plots were linear, giving $10^5 k_{\text{obs}} =$

$(19.62 \pm 0.1) \text{ s}^{-1}$ when $[\text{Cr}^{3+}]_T$ was changed from 0.003 to 0.006 mol dm^{-3} . The independence of k_{obs} at 50° under the condition $[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_T = 0.05$, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH} \approx 3.5$ over a $[\text{Cr}^{3+}]_T$ range from 3.0×10^{-3} to $6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ is in agreement with first order dependence on $[\text{Cr}^{3+}]_T$.

Effect of reaction rate on methanol content : In order to determine the influence of dielectric constant of the medium on the reaction rate, the anation reaction was studied in methanol-water solvent mixture. An increase in k_{obs} was observed as the dielectric constant (D) of the medium was decreased (Table 1). A plot of k_{obs} versus $1/D$ is linear indicating that the reaction species have opposite charge. According to Bjerrum equation¹⁰, the values of the outer sphere complex formation constant K_{OS} will increase with the decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium and therefore the outer-sphere-complexation is enhanced with consequent increase in the rate. The reaction sequence given below is consistent with the experimental data where O.S (outer-sphere complex) = $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{L}^+$.

Scheme

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{an}}[\text{O.S}]_e = k_{\text{an}}K_{\text{OS}}[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_e[\text{H}_2\text{L}^+]_e \quad (1)$$

$$= k_{\text{an}}K_{\text{OS}}K_1[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_e[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_e/[\text{H}^+] \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_T &= [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_e + [\text{O.S}]_e \\ &= [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_e + K_{\text{OS}} [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_e [\text{H}_2\text{L}^+]_e \\ &= [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_e \{1 + K_{\text{OS}}K_1[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_e/[\text{H}^+]\} \\ &= [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_e \{([\text{H}^+] + K_{\text{OS}}K_1[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_e)/[\text{H}^+]\} \\ [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_e &= [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_T [\text{H}^+]/ \\ &\quad \{([\text{H}^+] + K_{\text{OS}}K_1[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_e)\} \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_T &= [\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_e + [\text{H}_2\text{L}^+]_e \\ &= [\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_e + K_1[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_e/[\text{H}^+] \\ &= [\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_e \{([\text{H}^+] + K_1)/[\text{H}^+]\} \\ [\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_e &= [\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_T [\text{H}^+]/\{([\text{H}^+] + K_1)\} \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

Substituting the value of $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_e$ and $[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_e$ in eq. (2), we get :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \\ &= \frac{k_{\text{an}}K_{\text{OS}}K_1[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_T[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_T[\text{H}^+]}{([\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1 [\text{H}^+] + K_{\text{OS}} K_1 [\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_T [\text{H}^+])} \quad (5) \\ &= \frac{k_{\text{an}}K_{\text{OS}}K_1[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_T[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_T}{([\text{H}^+] + K_1 + K_{\text{OS}} K_1 ([\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_T)} \end{aligned}$$

Since we know that,

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}]_T \quad (6)$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_{\text{an}}K_{\text{OS}} K_1 [\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_T}{\{([\text{H}^+] + K_1) + K_{\text{OS}} K_1 [\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_T\}} \quad (7)$$

$$1/k_{\text{obs}} = 1/k_{\text{an}} + \{([\text{H}^+] + K_1)/(k_{\text{an}}K_{\text{OS}}K_1)\} \times 1/[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_T$$

The above mechanism was tested by plotting k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_T^{-1}$. The plots (Fig. 3) are linear ($r = 0.99$) for the anation reaction both at pH = 3.0 and 3.5 at 50°. The k_{an} was calculated from the reciprocal of the intercept and K_{OS} was calculated from the slope of the plot. The data are collected in Table 2. It is generally accepted that complex formation by metal ions proceeds by a mechanism in which the rate determining step is the change from outer-sphere complex to inner-sphere complex, preceded by the formation of the outer-sphere complex between the metal ion and ligand. Whether the interchange mechanism of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ is Ia or Id remains to be determined. The reaction path can be assigned Ia or Id if k_{an} is greater or less than the isotopic exchange rate constant¹¹ for $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$. The values of k_{an} at 25° is $0.64 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The far greater value of k_{an} compared to that of k_{ex} supports the proposition that the reaction of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ with L-ornithine follows the Ia path.

Fig. 3. $10^{-3}k_{\text{obs}}^{-1}/\text{s}$ versus $[\text{H}_3\text{L}^{2+}]_T^{-1}/\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$. Conditions : $[\text{Cr}^{3+}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KNO_3), at 50° : (1) at pH = 3.0 (2) at pH = 3.5.

The same conclusions can also be drawn by the comparison of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger of the exchange reaction with the ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger values $55.75 \pm 6.0 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-138.23 \pm 17.0 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively of the anation reaction between $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ and L-ornithine. The isokinetic plot (Fig. 4) stands as the testimony for the fact that, the same type of mechanism was followed for analogous substitution reactions involving various amino acids.

Characterisation of the product complex : A mixture of $0.005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ Cr}(\text{OH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_3$ and 0.02 mol dm^{-3} L-ornithine at pH 4.00 were heated over a water bath for 10 h. The resulting crystals were washed with ethanol and diethyl ether. Chromium was estimated by converting Cr^{3+} to Cr^{6+} and then estimating Cr^{6+} iodometrically. Nitrogen was estimated by improved Kjeldahl's method using Hoskin's apparatus.

The IR spectra were taken in a JASCO FT-IR-5300 spectrophotometer. In the substitution product, most of the peaks of ornithine retain their identity. The infra red stretching frequencies associated with the carboxylato proton of substituted product of ornithine appear at 1606 cm^{-1} , $\nu_{\text{str(S)}} \text{ C=O}$ and 1385 cm^{-1} , $\nu_{\text{str(W)}} \text{ C=O}$ with a 24 cm^{-1} and 59 cm^{-1} downshift from 1630 and 1444 cm^{-1} respectively. It indicates the coordination of carboxylato group to Cr^{3+} ion, through O-atom. A 35 cm^{-1} downshift from 1487 cm^{-1} to 1452 cm^{-1} for ν_{sym} bending for NH_3^+ is ascribed to bonding through N-atom. A strong band at 1637 cm^{-1} , $\nu_{\text{def}} (\text{O-H})$ and multiple bands at 3676 , 3528 , 3456 cm^{-1} $\nu_{\text{str}} (\text{O-H})$ were observed in the product which is an indication of water molecule occupy remaining four sites of

Table 2. Comparison of anation rate constants, k_{an} and activation parameters of $[\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ with amino acid.

Ligands	k_{an}/s^{-1} at 35°	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	Ref.
H ₂ O ¹⁸	4.17×10^{-6} (k_{ex})	110.0 ± 1	–	12
Glycine	6.80×10^{-4}	51.9	–42.7	15
Alanine	0.58×10^{-4}	64.9	–113.6	2(a), 14
Valine	2.35×10^{-4}	90.4	–21.0	1(b), (c), 13
Serine	0.62×10^{-4}	78.0	–72.5	1(b), (c), 13
Hasp	1.80×10^{-4}	81.0	–54.0	1(b), (c), 13
H ₂ asp	1.30×10^{-4}	50.0	–157.0	1(b), (c), 13
Hydroxyproline	1.00×10^{-4} (40°)	72.9	–98.2	2(a), 14
Phenylalanine	1.85×10^{-4}	53.6	–141.7	2(a), 14
Sarcosine	3.57×10^{-4} (40°)	54.7	–136.6	2(a), 14
Glutamine	1.81×10^{-4} (40°)	52.0	–150.6	Unpublished work
Methionine	2.22×10^{-4}	61.1	–116.3	2(a), 14
Tryptophan	1.17×10^{-4} (40°)	65.6	–112.4	9
L-Ascorbic acid	2.78×10^{-4} (40°)	27.0 ± 2	-227 ± 5	16
Nicotinic acid	10.24×10^{-4}	–	–	17
Dipicolinic acid	13.79×10^{-4}	–	–	17
L-Ornithine	1.70×10^{-4} (40°)	55.75 ± 6.0	-138 ± 17.0	This work
	3.42×10^{-4} (50°)			
	4.74×10^{-4} (55°)			

$$K_{OS}(\text{avg.}) = 18.86 \pm 0.34.$$

hexaqua chromium(III) ion. Besides, bands at 864 cm⁻¹ (water stretching) were observed indicating the presence of

Fig. 4. Isokinetic plots of ΔH^\ddagger versus ΔS^\ddagger for the anation of $[\text{Cr}(\text{OH}_2)_6]^{3+}$ by some amino acids : (1) glycine, (2) alanine, (3) valine, (4) serine, (5) Hasp, (6) H₂asp, (7) hydroxyproline, (8) phenylamine, (9) L-ornithine, (10) glutamine, (11) methionine, (12) tryptophan, (13) sarcosine.

coordinated water. From the individual assignment of different bands it can be presumed that the substituted species is monochelated. The tentative structure of the product is given in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Tentative structure of the product.

Expeimental

The complex solution of Cr^{3+} was prepared from $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (G.R.). Required amount of $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (G.R.) was taken in a beaker and it was dissolved in a definite volume of water. Dilute nitric acid was added to

the stock solution to make it acidic ($[H^+] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$).

The Cr^{3+} content in the solution was determined by ion-exchange and atomic absorption spectrophotometry methods. L-Ornithine monohydrochloride (SRL, India) was used without further purification. All the chemicals used for the kinetic run are A.R. or G.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used through out the reaction. pH of the solution was measured by Systronic 361 pH meter and absorbance by SHIMADZU UV-2101PC spectrophotometer.

The kinetics of the complexation of aquachromium(III) with L-ornithine monohydrochloride has been investigated and it was observed that, temperature, pH, L-ornithine and methanol content influenced the rate of the reaction. The ionic strength of the solution was adjusted using KNO_3 . The solution of L-ornithine at a desired pH was thermally equilibrated at a given temperature. Then the required amount of Cr^{3+} solution (previously equilibrated thermally) was added to the L-ornithine solution and placed in a thermostat, maintained at a definite temperature. The progress of the reaction was monitored at 570 nm. Pseudo-first order conditions were maintained throughout using a large excess (five-fold) of L-ornithine. The rate constants (k_{obs}) were obtained from the slopes of $\ln(A_\infty - A_t)$ vs t plots.

$$\ln(A_\infty - A_t) = \ln(A_\infty - A_0) - k_{obs}t$$

Here A_0 , A_t and A_∞ are the absorbance of the reaction at 570 nm at the beginning, at time t and at equilibrium respectively. The reported rate data represented as an average of duplicate runs were reproducible to within $\pm 5\%$. The correlation coefficient of plots used to determine k_{obs} were found to be 0.99 in most of the cases.

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